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CHAMPION Project Newsletter

Issue 1, January 2021

CHAMPION project – the first 6 months

CHAMPION is a 3.5 year project funded by the BBI JU and its 3 large industry partners. It includes [14 partners](#) from 6 European countries.

The aim of the project is to make sustainable, bio-based polymers that work at least as well as the existing fossil-based ones. What progress has been achieved in the first six months?

- Defining tangible aims - identifying and collecting the (type of) materials we want to replace
- Computer modelling of the materials – what are we aiming for?
- Setting up the testing – what will we do and what will it tell us?
- Concept testing - making some bio-based polymers and test if these work
- Sharing our story - launching the project website and using social media
- Stakeholder contact - linking with parties who want to be more involved with the project

Find out more on our website: www.champion-project.eu

Three CHAMPION partners are founding members of the Renewable Carbon Initiative

Led by CHAMPION project partner nova Institut, the [Renewable Carbon Initiative](https://www.renewable-carbon-initiative.com) was launched in September 2020 with Stahl and Unilever among the 12 advisory board members. The aim of the initiative is to accelerate the transition from fossil carbon to renewable carbon, through for example replacing petrochemical starting materials with bio-based ones.

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Single Use Plastics Directive comes into force

The CHAMPION project fits within the European aim to support more sustainable and safer consumption and production patterns for polymers. A key Directive with the same aim is the Single Use Plastics (SUP) Directive which has come into force on 1 January 2021.

The SUP Directive tackles marine litter coming from single-use plastics like cups, straws, bags, bottles or food packaging and includes the following measures:

- An EU-wide ban on products with readily available alternatives by mid-2021
- An obligation to reduce total consumption of products with currently less widely available alternatives by the year 2026
- Strengthening and complementing requirements for products already covered by existing EU legislation, such as packets, wrappers and beverage bottles
- Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes for various products

The CHAMPION project supports these measures by providing more sustainable and safer alternatives to fossil-based polymers. Although the CHAMPION project is not specifically targeting plastics, the research will develop new circular, degradable polymers that could offer potential in the applications highlighted by the SUP Directive.

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development of alternative plastic materials and recycling of plastics

CHAMPION project partner VTT Technical Research Centre (Espoo, Finland) has launched its piloting platform for process chemistry. The [VTT Bioruukki Pilot Centre](#) was established five years ago to help businesses to scale up development of new value-added products in a faster and lower-cost approach.

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Partners

- [University of York](#)
- [Wageningen Food & Biobased Research \(WFBR\)](#)
- [BioDetection Systems BV](#)
- [Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy](#)
- [Process Design Center BV](#)
- [OWS NV](#)
- [Circa Sustainable Chemicals Ltd](#)
- [Unilever UK Central Resources Ltd](#)
- [nova-Institut für Politische und Ökologische Innovation GmbH](#)
- [Ava Biochem BSL AG](#)
- [Stahl International BV](#)
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- [Scott Bader Co Ltd](#)

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